

INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES AND SELF-EFFICACY ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN LAGOS WEST SENATORIAL ZONE OF LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

EGBUNU, SUNDAY OJIMAOJO (Ph. D) and IJEOMA RITA OKEKE

EGBUNU, SUNDAY OJIMAOJO (Ph. D), Bingham University, Karu, Nasarawa State

IJEOMA RITA OKEKE, Angelite International School

Abstract

This study investigated the influence of parenting styles and self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. The population of this study was 254,119 SS II students from 34 senior secondary schools in Lagos West Senatorial Zone in Lagos State. The sample was 944, and a multistage sampling procedure was adopted for this work. Three instruments were developed and used for data collection. They were the Parenting Styles Questionnaire (PSQ), Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (SEQ), and Academic Achievement Test (AAT) in Mathematics and English Language. The instrument validity indices were 0.83 for PSQ, 0.75 for SEQ, and 0.85 for AAT. Their reliability indices for internal consistency were 0.83 for PSQ and 0.81 for SEQ, while AAT had 0.71. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while chi-square statistics were used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that parenting styles and self-efficacy have significant influence on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State. Hence, it was concluded that students' academic achievement is greatly influenced by parenting styles and self-efficacy among senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State. It was recommended that parents should ensure a blend of parenting styles, as no single style seems to single-handedly improve students' achievement in all situations. In addition, teachers, counsellors, and psychologists should use appropriate psychological interventions to handle test anxiety and create positive self-esteem to enhance the academic self-efficacy of secondary school students, which will help in improving their academic achievement.

Keywords: Parenting styles, self-efficacy, academic achievement.

Introduction

Parenting responsibility and responsiveness are key to children's nurturing and upbringing, which span from infancy, childhood, teenage years, adolescence, and even young adulthood, with concern for their physical, emotional, social, and all areas of life, especially academics, which serve as a vehicle for all-round human transformation

(Achema, 2012). Academic activities no doubt give room for the moulding, building, and assessment of students in the school system in all three domains of learning, which are cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. This assessment comes in the form of a test known as an achievement test, which could be categorized as standardized or teacher-made, based on who constructs the test.

Academic achievement has become an index of a child's future in this highly competitive world. Academic achievement has been one of the most important goals of the educational process. Academic achievement is a key mechanism through which students learn about their talents, abilities, and competencies, which are an important part of developing career aspirations. Crow and Crow (2009) defined academic achievement as "the extent to which learner is profiting from instructions in a given area of learning and instruction, achievement is reflected by the extent to which skill or knowledge has been imparted to him" (p. 126). Academic achievement is defined as the performance of the students in the subjects they study in school (Clark, 2013). A student's score in school subjects could be proof of his or her ability in the future and even in the labour force. This calls for the emphasis placed on students' scores in the learning process, and that is why low scores and poor achievement in school are concerns for parents, teachers, and society at large.

Poor academic achievement remains a matter of concern in the school system, irrespective of efforts made by various stakeholders to halt it. Despite the huge contribution of the Lagos State Government to the educational sector, poor academic achievement in secondary schools still stands as a great challenge to the state. This is because of the declining achievement rate among students. Recent reports from examination bodies, such as the West African Examinations Council and the National Examinations Council, revealed that only 40% to 47% of students had credit passes in Mathematics and English Language from 2019 to 2023. According to Mozaffari (2015), about 27% of senior secondary school students have low academic achievement in the core subjects in the WASSCE. Low academic achievement may create many negative consequences for students. Students with low academic achievement may be more vulnerable to problems such as stress, hopelessness, delinquency, psychopathology, and substance abuse (Assarian, 2016). However, parenting styles have been observed by researchers and some scholars as factors that could contribute to students' high or low achievement in school.

The concept of parenting styles was defined by Baumrind (2012) as behaviours, values, and standards that are transmitted to children, and these behaviours, values, and standards are expected to be adopted by children. These parenting styles have clear sets of objectives, rules, and standards for their children to follow, and such parents are attentive to their children's behaviour (Baumrind, 2012). Baumrind categorized parenting styles into four: authoritative parenting, authoritarian parenting, permissive parenting, and uninvolved parenting styles. The last style has become more necessary as a result of further studies conducted by Baumrind in 2012 to show that there could also be other styles that are neither authoritarian, authoritative, nor permissive, but exist as

uninvolved and could also be considered a parenting style. Spera (2015) asserted that parenting styles emphasize the responses parents provide to their children and the methods parents use to demand compliance from their children.

Authoritarian parenting style is a manner of parental control of children that is subject to strict conformity with guardian decisions and directions. This strict conformity with parental decisions tends to make the child disciplined in all areas, including academics, which could lead to improved achievement as a result of extreme discipline. However, this absolute and total control could cause students to lack creativity, which in turn can affect their academic achievement as well. Authoritative parenting style is less flexible; it is a situation where parents and children relate with much love and a high sense of respect. This probably makes the children self-reliant, self-assertive, independent, friendly, and cooperative in school. These personal qualities help in building relationships with other students, and through such interaction, knowledge is shared, which may improve achievement. However, in some cases, children tend to study less, which could then affect their achievement.

On the other hand, some parents are seen to adopt a permissive parenting style. In this approach, children are feared by parents who lack authority control, are inconsistent in principles, and are not demanding. Parents are often carefree in attitude and rarely employ punishment on their children. A permissive parent tends to offer as much freedom as the child wants, not demanding any form of conformity as long as the child's physical safety is not at risk. Furthermore, uninvolved parenting style is the style in which parents neglect their children by putting their own lives before the child's. They do not provide for the child's basic needs, and they show little interaction with the child. This may also have an effect on the academic performance of students (Aquilino, 2017). Students may not perform well under this parenting style, as they are easily distracted by things that make parents always check on them. However, a child under an uninvolved style may spend the whole day reading and studying his or her books in his or her room uninterrupted and, by so doing, outperform other students.

It is also worthy of mention that self-efficacy is equally a variable in the context of this work which may influence students' academic achievement. The concept of self-efficacy is related to the belief that everyone has to evaluate his or her ability to perform a given task successfully. This concept has a strong influence on the approach to the task, the persistence to accomplish it, as well as the level of effort. Self-efficacy in individuals is an important attribute necessary for the psychological development of students. Self-efficacy enhances the individual's confidence to progress. Chemers (2017) noted that self-efficacy is an important predictor of academic achievement. Rivers (2012) proposed that, along with certain cognitive and non-cognitive factors, individual factors like self-efficacy also have influence on the effective outcomes of students' academic performance.

At this juncture, it may seem very difficult to categorically say that a particular parenting style is the best and has superiority over others because this parenting pattern is deeply influenced by culture, and culture decides the limits of behaviour that are to be controlled and practiced. It is also true that the task of parenting is enormous and overburdening in

present-day circumstances owing to parents' tight and crowded schedules. Notwithstanding, it is important for parents to note that for their children to become good citizens of society, their role in inculcating discipline and good behaviour, irrespective of the parenting style practiced, is non-negotiable. Nevertheless, evidence has shown that parenting patterns and training influence children's societal way of life, but there is no such proof to show whether parenting styles and self-efficacy can influence the academic achievement of students in the study area under investigation. It is against this background that this study investigated the influence of parenting styles and self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Stakeholders are becoming worried about the poor academic achievement among students in the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and National Examinations Council (NECO), especially in Mathematics and English Language, particularly in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. Results by examination bodies show that achievement in Mathematics and English Language continues to drop every year from 2019 to 2023, as indicated: 2019, 24.85%; 2020, 38.81%; 2021, 35.57%; 2022, 31.28%; and 2023, 38.68%. Looking at it from the researcher's perspective, it could be assumed that parenting styles might be responsible for students' failure, since family influence on children could greatly affect their understanding, attitude, and academic work in school, but this has not been taken into cognizance by most parents due to the daily family hustling for livelihood that characterizes Lagos West Senatorial Zone in particular. Children, on their own part, approach academic tasks in school with fear and a nonchalant attitude.

It is believed that a child's upbringing has a profound influence on how he or she sees the world and how he or she processes information, especially as patterned by the family he or she comes from in society. Students' low achievement in Mathematics and English Language has delayed students' admission into tertiary institutions. It is expected that students must have credits in both Mathematics and English in addition to three other credits before they are admitted. While the problem persists, there is no empirical study in Lagos West Senatorial Zone to show that parenting styles and self-efficacy could be the cause of students' poor academic achievement. It is in light of this that the researcher investigated the influence of parenting styles and self-efficacy on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone, Lagos State.

The study was guided by the following research questions and hypotheses.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do parenting styles influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State?

2. What is the influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. Parenting style does not significantly influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State.
2. There is no significant influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was adopted for this study. This design is suitable for this study because the study investigated the influence of parenting styles and self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone in Lagos State. The target population of this study comprised all SS II students from 34 senior secondary schools in Lagos West Senatorial Zone in Lagos State, totalling 254,119, as contained in the record of Lagos State Education Authority (2022).

The sample for this study was 944, and it was adjudged adequate from Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table of specification for determining required sample size from a given population. The study adopted a multistage sampling procedure. The sampling began with the clustering of the study area into its 10 local government areas: Agege, Ajeromi Ifelodun, Alimosho, Amuwo Odofin, Badagry, Ifako Ijaiye, Ikeja, Mushin, Ojo, and Oshodi Isolo. Thereafter, five local government areas—Agege, Alimosho, Badagry, Ikeja, and Ojo—were selected from the 10 LGAs using the systematic sampling technique, maintaining an interval of 1. The third stage was the selection of 59 schools from the five LGAs by the use of the proportionate sampling technique. The last stage was the application of simple random sampling of lucky dip to select a total number of 944 students, which made up the sample.

Three instruments were used for data collection. The first was a questionnaire developed by the researcher titled Parenting Styles Questionnaire (PSQ). The questionnaire had only one section clustered into four segments of authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and uninvolved, depicting the indices of the independent variable. It consisted of 20 items constructed to elicit responses of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree, with 4, 3, 2, and 1 points allocated to each in that order. The second instrument was also a researcher-developed questionnaire known as Self-Efficacy Questionnaire (SEQ). It consisted of 10 items framed to elicit responses of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree, with 4, 3, 2, and 1 points allocated to each in that order.

The third instrument was the Academic Achievement Test (AAT) in Mathematics and English Language. The Mathematics and English tests were based on the SS 2 scheme of work. Both Mathematics and English tests consisted of 20 items each, represented in multiple-choice options a, b, c, and d, to which participants were expected to respond. The researcher used students' scores in English Language and Mathematics achievement tests administered to them as the academic achievement. The questionnaire and achievement test were given to all the respondents with an identification pairing number for easy collation.

The questionnaires were presented to two experts in the Faculty of Education, Nasarawa State University, Keffi, for content and construct validity. The experts subjected them to critical appraisal, which gave the logical validity indices of 0.83 for PSQ and 0.75 for SEQ, depicting that the instruments were valid enough for the study. The Academic Achievement Test on Mathematics and English had 0.85.

The instrument was pilot-tested at Oshodi Grammar School on 30 students who were not part of the sample for this study. The data obtained from the pilot test were used to compute the internal consistency of the instrument using the Cronbach alpha coefficient method. The Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.83 was obtained for PSQ and 0.81 for SEQ. The coefficient was considered high, meaning that the instrument was reliable to be used in this research. The reliability for the Academic Achievement Test on Mathematics and English Language produced 0.71, having been subjected to Kuder-Richardson (KR-20/21).

The researchers, accompanied by two research assistants who were earlier trained on the instruments, introduced themselves to the principals using introductory letters. The researcher explained to the respondents the purpose of the study before administering the questionnaires to the sampled schools and administered the instruments at various schools. The researcher used the "wait-and-take" technique to collect the data, as the students were given verbal instructions where necessary. All the instruments were given pairing identification numbers before being distributed to the students in their schools. Data obtained from the administration of the questionnaires were collected for analysis. The retrieval rate was 100% as a result of the wait-and-take technique employed. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while chi-square statistics were used to test hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent does parenting style influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics on the Influence of Parenting Style on Senior Secondary School Students Achievement in Lagos West Senatorial Zone

Authoritarian Parenting Style	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std.D
1. My parents allow me to question their decisions.	458	198	106	182	2.99	1.17
2. My parents feel that if they force me, I would behave the way they want.	406	213	175	150	2.93	1.12
3. My parents take my opinions into consideration when discussing my academics.	503	200	155	86	3.19	1.01
4. My parents allow me to make decisions regarding my academics.	237	225	232	250	2.48	1.13
5. My parents do not blame me for anything that is wrong with my study.	426	196	197	125	2.98	1.09
Grand Mean & Std Deviation					2.91	1.10

Table 1 shows respondents' ratings on the extent to which different parenting styles influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. The result reveals that, with a mean cut-off point of 2.50 and above used as the benchmark, parenting styles have influence on secondary school students' academic achievement in Lagos West Senatorial Zone.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone?

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on the Influence of Self-Efficacy on Senior Secondary School Students Achievement in Lagos West Senatorial Zone

Self-Efficacy	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.D
1. I believe I will have an excellent score in my examination.	653	140	75	76	3.45	.944
2. I am certain I can understand difficult topics on these subjects.	644	141	88	71	3.44	.941
3. I am confident I can understand basic concepts on these subjects.	553	163	90	138	3.20	1.108

Self-Efficacy	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std.D
4. I am confident I will pass my examination very well because of my ability.	436	166	142	200	2.89	1.204
5. I believe I can do any assignment given to me by my teachers without assistance from others.	374	171	192	207	2.75	1.191
6. I expect to do very well in all my subjects.	380	153	168	243	2.71	1.236
7. I am certain I can master my study materials with little coaching from my teachers.	364	144	186	250	2.66	
8. No matter the difficulty of the learning materials, with my skills and ability, I think I will do well, no doubt.	379	116	201	248		1.246
Grand Mean					2.86	1.156

Table 2 shows the influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. The result reveals that item 1 had a mean score of 3.45; item 2 had a mean score of 3.44; item 3 had a mean score of 3.20; item 4 had a mean score of 2.89; item 5 had a mean score of 2.75; item 6 had a mean score of 2.71; and item 7 had a mean score of 2.66. These are all above the 2.50 benchmark.

Testing of Hypotheses

H0₁: Parenting styles have no significant influence on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone.

Table 3: Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Parenting Style on the Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone

Variables		Std. D	df	Alpha (α)	χ ² cal	P-value	Decision
Parenting Styles Academic Ach.	14.55	2.51	942	0.05	287.18	.042	Reject HO ₁
	26.82	4.59					

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows significant influence; PS = Parenting Styles.

Table 3 above shows the chi-square statistic (χ^2) on the influence of parenting styles on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. The result is given as: [N = 944, $\chi^2 = 287.18$, $p < .05$ (.042)]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore rejected. This means that parenting styles have significant influence on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone.

HO₂: Self-efficacy will not significantly influence the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Mathematics and English Language in Lagos West Senatorial Zone.

Table 4: Chi-Square Statistics on the Influence of Self-Efficacy on the Academic Achievement of Senior Secondary School Students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone

Variables		Std. D	df	Alpha (α)	χ ² cal	P-value	Decision
Self-Efficacy * Academic Ach.	29.62	4.21	942	0.05	470.95	.027	Reject HO ₂
	26.82	4.59					

Level of significance $\alpha < 0.05$ shows significant influence; Ach: Achievement.

Table 4 above shows the chi-square statistic (χ^2) on the influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. The result is given as: [N = 944, $\chi^2 = 470.95$, $p < .05$ (0.027)]. The formulated hypothesis was therefore rejected. This means that self-efficacy has a significant influence on the academic achievement of secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone.

Discussion of Findings

Findings from the study on hypothesis one reveal that there is a significant influence of authoritarian parenting style on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. This is supported by Odongo (2016), whose study

found that parenting style significantly predicted the academic performance of adolescents. Yaman (2015) found that authoritarian and authoritative parenting styles made significant contributions to students' academic achievement. Findings from the study by Ahmad, Emmanuel, and Yakubu (2019) showed that the parents of secondary school students in Anambra State appear to be more authoritarian and laissez-faire and less democratic. The dominant parenting style is authoritarian. This may be due to the Nigerian nature, where our parents most times dominate and want to have the final say in whatever concerns their children. There was equally no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and academic achievement of secondary school students in Anambra State. The study also discovered that there was a significant relationship between laissez-faire and democratic parenting styles and students' academic achievement in Anambra State.

Findings from the study on hypothesis two show that there is a significant influence of self-efficacy on the academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone. This is in accord with the result of Adeoye and Feyisetan (2015), whose study showed that self-concept and self-efficacy jointly and relatively contributed to the academic achievement in English Language of the participants. Ogunmakin and Akomolafe's (2018) study also corroborates the findings of this study through multiple regression analysis. The researchers found that academic self-efficacy predicted academic performance. Further analysis revealed that self-efficacy significantly predicted academic performance, while locus of control was not a good predictor. Their results equally revealed that there is a statistically significant relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic performance among university undergraduate students.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that students' academic achievement is greatly influenced by parenting styles and self-efficacy among senior secondary school students in Lagos West Senatorial Zone of Lagos State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made as a result of the findings:

1. The study recommends that parents should ensure a blend of parenting styles, as no single style seems to single-handedly improve students' achievement in all situations.
2. Teachers, counsellors, and psychologists should use appropriate psychological interventions to handle test anxiety and create positive self-esteem to enhance the academic self-efficacy of secondary school students, which will help in improving their academic achievement.

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